

RESEARCH ARTICLE

CLINT: Controller-Assisted Lightweight In-Band Network Telemetry

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ABSTRACT The increasing need for high-precision monitoring and network-wide observability has spurred significant interest in In-Band Network Telemetry (INT), which empowers the collection of monitoring data directly from the dataplane, thus, alleviating the various shortcomings of passive monitoring techniques. INT, in some of its initial forms (*e.g.*, P4-INT), tends to accumulate per-hop telemetry values within each packet, introducing substantial transmission overhead. Recent efforts to alleviate this shortcoming spread per-hop telemetry values among multiple packets, but eventually cause other implications, such as INT data redundancy or collisions during state lookup, stemming from the probabilistic data structures that they employ. Along these lines, we stress on the need for a lightweight INT approach with deterministic behavior. To this end, we present a new INT approach (Controller-Assisted Lightweight In-Band Network Telemetry – CLINT) that relies on a telemetry controller for the coordination of INT nodes, through the update of telemetry states, which indicate at each instance the telemetry action that should be applied to each incoming packet. We discuss in detail the operation of CLINT, as well as its prototype implementation using P4 BMv2 and the P4Runtime API. Our evaluation results indicate that CLINT outperforms two state-of-the-art lightweight INT techniques (*i.e.*, PINT and DLINT) in terms of monitoring efficiency and network update detection, while maintaining an insignificant control communication overhead.

INDEX TERMS In-band network telemetry (INT), network monitoring, software-defined networks, programmable dataplanes.

I. INTRODUCTION

Recent trends in networking, such as network slicing and softwarisation, have improved the ability of modern networks to cope with the strict and often diverse application requirements [1], [2], [3], [4], [5], [6], [7]. However, at the same time, they introduce additional complexity both in terms of management and monitoring. This is further exacerbated by the increasing scale of networks, such as cloud datacenters and telco networks.

High-precision monitoring is gaining more significance nowadays, considering the pressing need for observability across the network [8], *e.g.*, for compliance with

Service-Level Agreements (SLAs) established among operators and their customers. Traditionally, monitoring systems employ active or passive techniques. Active monitoring [9], [10] is associated with probing techniques, *i.e.*, probe packets that are periodically injected to the network in order to measure the network performance (*e.g.*, throughput, latency). Apparently, this approach yields a considerable overhead in the network.

Due to this shortcoming, network monitoring systems more often rely on passive techniques (primarily, *pull-based*) [9], [10], at which a monitoring node or controller retrieves information from network devices (*e.g.*, by querying the counters of switch ports). This approach can introduce bandwidth consumption, which depends on the granularity of monitoring. To alleviate this implication, pull-based

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monitoring systems are configured to collect monitoring information in the order of tens of seconds or even minutes. Such coarse-grained monitoring may not be sufficient, *e.g.*, for the detection of transient network implications, such as short-lived congestion events. In addition, observability is hard to be attained, especially in dynamically changing network environments (*e.g.*, edge clouds) where services and network flows tend to have relatively short lifetime.

In-band network telemetry (INT) comprises a recent monitoring approach, which aims at alleviating the shortcomings of active and passive monitoring techniques [11], [12], [13], [14], [15], [16], [17], [18], [19]. More specifically, INT leverages on programmable dataplane technologies (*i.e.*, P4 programming language [20]) for the encapsulation of telemetry indicators (*e.g.*, switch IDs, buffer occupancy, link utilization) into packets. As such, P4 switches can be instructed (using P4 code) to insert, update, or remove telemetry headers, based on the needs of each particular telemetry application (*e.g.*, encapsulation of switch IDs for path tracing). INT commonly relies on telemetry servers (deployed at egress points) for the collection of telemetry data inserted by P4 switches. As such, INT constitutes a viable approach for fine-grained network monitoring using the dataplane. This can provide much better visibility in the network, facilitating the detection of congestion events, routing misconfigurations, links with high utilization, and other network problems, which usually degrade application performance with implications visible to end-users.

That said, INT also exhibits its own limitations, especially in the form of P4-INT [21], which empowers P4 switches to encode telemetry metadata into a pre-defined telemetry header, which is encapsulated into each packet as soon as it has entered into a so-called INT domain (*i.e.*, a network domain whose devices support INT functionalities). The main shortcoming of P4-INT stems from the transmission overhead that it can introduce into each packet [11], [12]. For instance, in term of path tracing, P4-INT will end up encapsulating all hop IDs within each single packet. As such, the space occupied by the telemetry header within each packet can increase substantially with long paths, introducing a severe restriction in the payload size, given the Maximum Transmission Unit (MTU) limitations imposed by protocols such as the Ethernet.

Certain INT techniques address this issue, based on the intuition that certain telemetry metadata (*e.g.*, per-hop information such as hop IDs, timestamps) can be spread among the packets of a flow [11], [12]. This form of per-flow aggregation can eliminate telemetry metadata redundancy among the packets of a flow and, more importantly, can alleviate the transmission overhead introduced by INT mechanisms, such as P4-INT.

Per-flow aggregation has fueled the design of various INT frameworks that aspire to maintain a compact INT header (*e.g.*, [11], [12], [19]). Nevertheless, these lightweight INT approaches exhibit certain shortcomings and implications.

More specifically, probabilistic INT techniques, such as PINT [11] and PLINT [12], tend to insert redundant telemetry values into packets, wasting INT header space and eventually prolonging the collection of monitoring information by the telemetry server. Other lightweight INT techniques that rely on INT node coordination suffer from collisions, due to the probabilistic data structures that they employ (*e.g.*, count-min sketch, Bloom filters [12], [19]).

Based on these observations, we stress on the need for a lightweight INT approach with deterministic behavior. To this end, we propose a new lightweight INT framework, namely Controller-Assisted Lightweight In-Band Network Telemetry (CLINT), where a centralized telemetry controller augments the spreading of telemetry metadata among all the packets of each monitored flow, based on telemetry states maintained within P4 switch registers. The controller intervention is insignificant, *i.e.*, it is restricted in the telemetry setup, facilitating the reservation of telemetry state space in the switch registers on per-flow basis. CLINT builds upon INT coordination techniques (*i.e.*, telemetry states) that were introduced in our previous work (DLINT [12]). That said, CLINT constitutes a new controller-assisted approach that exhibits a deterministic behavior, as corroborated by our experimental results.

We perform a comparison of CLINT against two other state-of-the-art INT techniques that also aim at the reduction of transmission overhead, but unlike our approach, without the intervention of a centralized controller. More specifically, we quantify the monitoring efficiency of our proposed INT technique in comparison to a coordinated (*i.e.*, DLINT [12]) and uncoordinated (*i.e.*, PINT [11]) approach to lightweight INT. Through an extensive experimental study, we gain various insights in terms of telemetry data density, INT header space utilization, redundancy among telemetry values spread within the same packet and across multiple packets, as well as responsiveness to network update incidents such as path updates. Overall, CLINT compares very favorably against these representative INT methods, exhibiting high efficiency across a range of evaluation scenarios. A significant benefit of CLINT is its ability to eliminate telemetry data redundancy, as opposed to other lightweight INT techniques (such as the ones that we use in our comparison) that tend to suffer from this issue.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Section II introduces the main functionality of INT, whereas Section III provides an overview of related work. In Section IV, we introduce the main design aspects of CLINT, such as the telemetry states. In Section V, we discuss in detail the operation of CLINT, including the telemetry setup and the switch coordination for the spreading of telemetry data among packets. Section VI discusses incremental updates in CLINT to support multiple telemetry values and also clarifies the impact of path asymmetry and path updates in the operation of CLINT. In Section VII, we describe our CLINT prototype implementation. In Section VIII, we present our evaluation results and provide insights into

FIGURE 1. INT header over TCP in INT-MD mode.

the operation and efficiency of CLINT. Finally, Section IX highlights our conclusions.

II. IN-BAND NETWORK TELEMETRY

INT emerged from the the P4 Language Consortium [21]. More specifically, INT defines a shim header that can be inserted between TCP/IP headers, along with telemetry metadata. Telemetry metadata may include switch IDs, congestion data, queue/buffer occupancy, per-hop latency, ingress/egress port, timestamps, etc. The INT header can also carry INT instructions that designate which telemetry metadata should be encoded into each packet by a switch.

A. INT TERMINOLOGY

As mentioned earlier, the part of network that supports INT functionalities is commonly termed as INT domain. According to the INT specification, INT nodes can have one of the following roles:

- **INT Source**, which is the first INT-enabled device (*e.g.*, P4 switch, SmartNIC with P4 support) that a packet encounters on its way to its destination. The INT source is mainly responsible for the encapsulation of an INT header into the packet.
- **INT Transit**, which corresponds to each intermediate INT node that is entitled with the update of specific values in the telemetry header of each incoming packet.
- **INT Sink**, which designates an egress point of the INT domain (*i.e.*, the last device with INT functionality). An INT sink strips the telemetry header and forwards it to a telemetry server.

P4-INT supports the three following operational modes, which correspond to three discrete scales of INT:

- **Export Data (INT-XD)**, where data packets remain intact, but switches are programmed to forward specific telemetry data to the telemetry server. This mode is also known as *postcard* mode.

FIGURE 2. Example of path tracing with P4-INT.

- **Embed Instructions (INT-MX)**, where packets carry an INT header with instructions only, guiding the switch to forward specific telemetry data to the telemetry server.
- **Embed Data (INT-MD)**, where both instructions and telemetry data are inserted into the data packet. In this mode, a P4 switch inserts or updates telemetry data within the packet, based on the instructions encoded in the INT header.

INT defines a shim header that incorporates all the necessary telemetry information for each operational mode. Fig. 1 depicts the corresponding header for INT-MD in TCP. More precisely, the INT shim header contains the length and type of the header, followed by the metadata header which contains instructions for the switch, including the type of data that it should insert into the metadata stack. In addition, the INT header can store the actual metadata stacked from all nodes that the packet has traversed. P4-INT can encapsulate its header into a wide range of protocols, such as TCP, UDP, Geneve [22], GRE, VXLAN, and Network Service Header (NSH) [23].

B. INT OVERHEAD

We hereby discuss the problem of transmission overhead that P4-INT introduces, in relation to various telemetry applications. To exemplify this problem, consider the application of INT-MD for path tracing, where the sequence of hops that a packet traverses should be encoded within the INT header. We illustrate a simple INT-MD path tracing example in Fig. 2. In particular, a packet reaches *node1*, which acts as the INT Source by inserting an INT header into the packet, along with its hop ID. Subsequently, *node2* inserts its own ID on top of the hop-sequence stack within the INT header. Similarly, each downstream INT node performs the same action, till the packet has reached *node4*, which, as the INT Sink, extracts all telemetry data from the packet, strips the INT header, and conveys the telemetry values to the telemetry server. This INT process is visible only to the nodes within the INT domain, and transparent to the end-points, as well as to any other nodes outside of the INT domain boundaries.

Although the aforementioned INT process is successful in utilizing the data plane for the delivery of path traces to the telemetry server, there is an undesirable implication. More precisely, the hop-by-hop insertion of telemetry values into

the packet inevitably inflates the INT header. In essence, the INT header grows proportionally with the path hop-count. Besides the excessive transmission overhead, MTU limitations may trigger packet fragmentation, which entails additional processing overhead in the switches and potential latency inflation. The extra transmission overhead can also diminish application performance (*i.e.*, reduce goodput) [24].

As the mitigation of this problem is imperative for the application of INT in a scalable and robust fashion, various INT methods have exercised deterministic and probabilistic approaches, aiming at spreading telemetry values across multiple packets (*e.g.*, [12], [14], [24]). Since most of existing INT approaches either rely on the data plane for INT node coordination or perform INT actions based on probabilities (both of which yield certain shortcomings, as we discuss in Section III), in this paper, we present a new lightweight INT approach with a minimum controller intervention, aspiring to remedy the implications of existing INT methods.

III. RELATED WORK

In this section, we provide an overview of existing INT techniques. To facilitate the positioning with our work (which utilizes a controller for the coordination among INT nodes), we classify the various INT approaches into (i) controller-assisted and (ii) data-plane based. In this respect, we clarify that *controller-assisted* implies that the controller intervenes in the telemetry metadata encapsulation, instead of merely defining INT parameters or collecting data, which pertains to most INT methods.

A. CONTROLLER-ASSISTED INT

Selective-INT seeks to mitigate the problem of P4-INT transmission overhead [25]. To this end, telemetry data is inserted only into certain packets of a flow. The packet selection for telemetry data is based on a variable ratio factor, which is increased whenever a path update is detected or reduced when no network events occur. Selective-INT keeps track of every flow by hashing its 5-tuple and storing its state in the switch. This INT method suffers from the limited memory of P4 switches and hash collisions, whereas the telemetry header growth may trigger packet fragmentation. Sel-INT relies on an approach similar to Selective-INT, but utilizes Protocol Oblivious Forwarding for its operation [15].

C-INT [26] avoids the enlargement of INT header within packets by periodically offloading telemetry information. More specifically, the network is subdivided into clusters using a clustering algorithm. Packets traverse several clusters before reaching their destination, while incorporating telemetry data. The metadata stack is being forwarded to the collector of each cluster, which, in turn, conveys it to the central telemetry server. As such, the INT header is not overinflated, whereas the INT sink does not take the burden of forwarding all telemetry data to the telemetry server. Furthermore, C-INT manages to avoid MTU fragmentation, by preserving dense per-packet data collection. However, these benefits can be outweighed by the overhead of

managing clusters with special headers and cluster-to-server communication.

B. DATAPLANE-BASED INT

In the following, we discuss INT techniques that seek to reduce the INT transmission overhead without the intervention of a controller. Some INT methods employ probabilistic approaches, obviating the need for coordination among INT nodes. Although this approach entails less complexity, eventually it can diminish the accuracy of monitoring data that is conveyed to the telemetry server.

In situ Operations, Administration, and Maintenance (IOAM) comprises an INT technique proposed by IETF [27]. IOAM encapsulates telemetry data into packets similar to P4-INT. Telemetry data is inserted using a specific header structure. The INT nodes perform telemetry actions without any coordination from a controller. IOAM prototypes are available for Linux-based and Cisco routers.

PINT employs a probabilistic approach for the distribution of telemetry data among packets [24]. More specifically, PINT allows the administrator to choose how much header space will be allocated for telemetry data. Every switch chooses whether to insert its telemetry information based on a probability. To ensure an equal probability among all INT nodes, PINT leverages on reservoir sampling. The probabilistic nature of PINT inevitably introduces some redundancy among the telemetry data encoded into packets (*e.g.*, applying INT for path tracing may convey multiple times the same hop ID). This redundancy can prolong the collection of telemetry data by the telemetry server.

DLINT relies on INT node coordination, such that each node is aware which action(s) to perform (*e.g.*, insert a telemetry value) upon each incoming packet [12]. This is achieved through per-flow telemetry states maintained within the INT nodes. More precisely, DLINT utilizes the following three telemetry states: (i) *Awaiting Init*, where the INT node waits for an INIT signal in order to insert telemetry data, (ii) *Ready to Insert ID*, where the INT node is ready to insert its data into the following incoming packet of the respective flow, and (iii) *Inserted ID*, where the INT node has already inserted its own telemetry data and waits for a signal to revert to the initial state (*Awaiting Init*) in order to re-insert subsequent telemetry value(s). To reduce the amount of telemetry state that needs to be maintained within each INT node, DLINT utilizes Bloom Filters (BF). BF manages a substantial compression of the state space at the expense of collisions during state lookup that can impair the monitoring accuracy of DLINT. This implication is not occurring in CLINT, due to the utilization of a centralized telemetry controller for the allocation of registers within P4 switches.

AM-PM constitutes another INT method proposed by IETF [28]. AM-PM relies on hybrid in- and out-of-band methods for the monitoring of packet loss, delay, and jitter. To this end, specific packets are being *colored* with an indicative header field. These *colored* packets instruct the switch to

conduct measurements and send the corresponding data to a server, which subsequently processes the measurements and timestamps in order to calculate delay, jitter, etc. Although the INT header size is minimum, processing and storage space needs to be utilized in switches for this method.

FS-INT alleviates the overhead of P4-INT by sampling packets where telemetry data is inserted [14]. Sampling can be conducted either with a fixed rate or alternatively can be event-based. In the first case, switches are configured with a predefined rate for choosing which packets will carry telemetry data. The event-based method is triggered by a specific delay condition in a switch. As long as this condition is met, telemetry data is inserted into packets. Although FS-INT reduces the overall INT header space, packets are inflated with data from all traversing switches, in both cases.

FINT proposes a method for the encapsulation of telemetry data in a more flexible manner [14]. More specifically, the administrator can dynamically modify the telemetry data being collected, as well as its distribution among packets. This is achieved using three bitmaps, which can rapidly communicate the type of INT data that should be inserted into the packets. In particular, one of the bitmaps defines whether switch ID, port, timestamp, delay, etc. should be inserted, while the corresponding bitmap in the packets designates what INT data has been inserted and pending. This mechanism distributes telemetry data among multiple packets, thus avoiding the inflation of packets with oversized INT data.

GPINT collects non path-dependent telemetry information from the switches [29]. To this end, GPINT employs graph-partitioning heuristic algorithms in order to identify the most efficient path over which a probe packet is being sent. The probe collects multiple telemetry variables from all switches and reports them to the telemetry server. Paths with more recent telemetry data are preferred.

SketchINT couples the benefits of INT and sketches [19]. Sketches can achieve data compression, thereby conserving bandwidth. Upon telemetry data insertion, the network card encodes this information into sketches, collects them and once they have become inactive, they are delivered to the Analyzer. As such, per-packet data is aggregated forming per-flow data.

In LINT [13], each device checks the margin between the current telemetry value against the value expected by a telemetry collector. When there is a significant margin, telemetry data is conveyed to the collector. As such, the INT transmission overhead is reduced in comparison with P4-INT. The performance of LINT depends on the threshold of the prediction function, as well as the variability of the monitored value.

There are also other INT methods that collect only stateless metadata about the internal state of a switch, such as INT-label [17]. In INT-label, each switch sends proactively or upon request data reporting network parameters to the telemetry server. The frequency of the reporting data can be adjusted dynamically using probabilistic labeling. Packet loss

FIGURE 3. Spreading of telemetry data across multiple packets with CLINT (right) vs. the accumulation of telemetry data within a single packet with P4-INT (left), based on a path tracing example.

FIGURE 4. CLINT states (in ellipses) and their transition from one to another along with the corresponding signals (in rectangles).

and inflation are also considered, so that telemetry data is not sparse. This probabilistic approach reduces the amount of telemetry packets.

IV. CLINT OVERVIEW

In this section, we present a new approach to lightweight INT, with the aim of maintaining a small and invariant telemetry header, where useful telemetry values can be inserted as packets traverse INT nodes towards their destination. Similar to other INT methods (e.g., [11], [12]), the INT header size can be reduced based on the intuition that instead of accumulating multiple telemetry values into the same packet, this information can be spread among multiple packets of a flow (Fig. 3). Since the telemetry data carried within each packet is delivered by the INT sink to the telemetry server, the latter can compose the required monitoring information (e.g., a path trace out of individual hop IDs delivered by separate packets).

The main innovative feature of our INT approach lies in the utilization of a controller for the coordination of INT nodes, such that each INT node (i.e., P4 switch) knows exactly which telemetry action it should apply to each incoming packet. We point out that the controller intervention is minimal so as to (i) avoid imposing unnecessary load to the controller, which could potentially introduce scalability limitations and (ii) maintain low control communication overhead.

The coordination among INT nodes takes place using telemetry states, which are maintained and updated on per-flow basis. More specifically, CLINT uses the following telemetry states:

- **SETUP.** The *Setup* state designates the completion of telemetry setup on each INT node. As we explain later on (Section V-A), telemetry setup is completed as soon as the controller has reserved telemetry state space in the INT node's register array.
- **READY.** This represents an initialization state for a new round of INT metadata insertion. In essence, this state is a prerequisite for repeated recording of monitoring data (e.g., in the context of path tracing, it enables the continuous tracing of the path over the entire duration of each flow).
- **INSERT.** This state indicates that the INT node can insert telemetry metadata (e.g., node ID) to the next packet of a flow.
- **INSERTED.** A transition to this state is invoked, as soon as an INT node has inserted its telemetry metadata to a packet. In essence, this state designates the completion of a telemetry insertion round. A transition to the next round (i.e., *READY* state) is triggered, upon the reception of a *RESET* signal (Fig. 4).

CLINT relies on P4 switches and, in particular, utilizes their registers to store the above telemetry states for each monitored flow. The exact position of the telemetry state of a flow is chosen by the telemetry controller, as we explain in detail in Section V-A.

The transitioning between telemetry states is controlled using dedicated signals that are inserted and carried by data packets. These signals, which essentially instruct INT nodes to switch to another state, are:

- **FIN-SETUP.** This signal indicates the progress of INT setup. When this signal has reached the last INT node on a flow's path, this implies that the setup phase has been completed for that flow. The *FIN-SETUP* signal is always emitted by the first INT node on the path.
- **INIT.** The *INIT* signal sets each INT node to the *INSERT* state, meaning that it can insert INT data into the next packet of the flow.
- **RESET.** This signal empowers repeated monitoring by advancing INT data encapsulation into the next round. For example, in terms of path tracing, a *RESET* signal initiates the recording of a new path trace by setting the telemetry state of all INT nodes from *INSERTED* to *READY* (Fig. 4). The *RESET* signal is emitted by the last INT node on the path, traversing all INT nodes in the reverse direction of data traffic.

Fig. 4 illustrates the telemetry states, as well as the roles of the above signals in the transitioning among these states.

V. CLINT OPERATION

Hereby, we describe in detail the operation of CLINT, which we decompose into a *Setup* and a *Monitoring* phase. The former encompasses all interactions between INT nodes and the controller for the reservation of telemetry state space in all INT nodes that reside on a flow's path. The *Monitoring* phase deals with the repeated insertion of INT metadata

into packets by exercising per-flow aggregation (Fig. 3). Note that although we rely on path tracing in order to exemplify the operation of CLINT, its applicability is not restricted to this telemetry application. Instead, CLINT can be utilized for other applications that require the collection of per-hop monitoring information (e.g., switch port utilization, timestamps).

A. SETUP PHASE

Inline with the capabilities of P4 switches, we consider that each INT node is equipped with a register array, where telemetry states are maintained for all monitored flows. Since the required telemetry states are four, two bits are sufficient.

The *Setup* phase of CLINT is illustrated in Fig. 5. As soon as new flow has been detected by an INT node (flows are distinguished based on the widely used 5-tuple), the latter sends a digest message to the controller with the flow's 5-tuple (*step1* for INT node1). Upon the reception of the digest message, the controller (which keeps track of the register arrays of all nodes within the INT domain), reserves an available register slot and informs the INT node (*step2*). The slot is initialized with 0, which corresponds to the *SETUP* state (*step3*).

After the *SETUP* state has been set for the first INT node on the path,¹ the INT node encodes a *FIN-SETUP* signal into the packets of the flow. Note that the *FIN-SETUP* signal is propagated by the other INT nodes on the path, only if they have completed their telemetry setup in collaboration with the controller (*node2* and *node3* in the example of Fig. 5). In case that the controller has not yet allocated any slot within an INT node's register array, the INT node in question removes the *FIN-SETUP* signal from each incoming packet of the flow (*node4* in Fig. 5). As such, the arrival of a *FIN-SETUP* signal at the last INT node on the path designates the completion of the telemetry setup phase.

However, for the transitioning to the monitoring phase (Section V-B), another step is required. More precisely, a *RESET* signal is emitted from the last INT node on the path, which traverses all INT nodes in the reverse direction, setting them to the *READY* state.² This essentially triggers the initiation of the first round of monitoring. Later on, we will see that the *RESET* signal is also utilized during the monitoring phase in order to advance CLINT to the next round of telemetry metadata insertion. Note that, in our prototype implementation, CLINT operates over TCP. Besides the fact that TCP is currently the dominant transport protocol, this decision allows CLINT to benefit from TCP piggybacking (i.e., the *RESET* signal is encoded within TCP ACK packets).

¹The first node of the path is identified through ingress ports that are connected to other switches or hosts outside of the INT domain. Hence, any traffic received from these ports is considered to encounter the first INT node on the path.

²As soon as the first INT node has been set to the *READY* state, it stops emitting the *FIN-SETUP* signal.

FIGURE 5. Setup phase of CLINT.

We point out that the *Setup* phase is taking place only once at the beginning of a each flow. When the path has been set up (telemetry-wise), CLINT monitors the flow exclusively via the data plane. After the end of a monitored flow, the telemetry controller reallocates the registry slot to another flow. This recycling of P4 registers leads to considerable memory conservation for each P4 switch.

To avoid any performance degradation during the *Setup* phase, CLINT decouples the telemetry setup from packet forwarding. More specifically, the INT nodes keep forwarding packets to their destination during the telemetry setup. As such, CLINT avoids packet buffering within switches (e.g., such buffering is common in OpenFlow switches during the handling of *PACKET-IN* messages by the controller). A downside of this approach is that the initial packets of a flow may be forwarded without any telemetry data. Nevertheless, this is inline with several INT methods that exercise sampling, inserting telemetry values only into a subset of packets (e.g., [14]). In the case of CLINT, we consider that this implication is minor, especially for the monitoring of long-lived flows.

B. MONITORING PHASE

The *Monitoring* phase is associated with the insertion of telemetry data into the incoming packets. As mentioned earlier, monitoring should occur repeatedly in order to feed the telemetry server with telemetry data over the entire flow duration. To this end, the notion of per-flow aggregation is applied over consecutive rounds. For instance, in terms of path tracing, each individual round of CLINT delivers a separate path trace. As such, any change in a flow’s path

FIGURE 6. Telemetry data encapsulation during the monitoring phase. Upon the insertion of its telemetry value (hop ID in this example), each INT node transitions from the *INSERT* to the *INSERTED* state.

can be promptly detected at the telemetry server. Other implications, such as (transient) congestion events or routing misconfigurations, can be also identified through the repeated recording of timestamps or port utilization.

The *Monitoring* phase encompasses transitions between the telemetry states *READY*, *INSERT*, and *INSERTED*, which are invoked using the *INIT* and *RESET* signals, as depicted in Fig. 4. More specifically, the *Monitoring* phase follows the completion of the *Setup* phase, after which all INT nodes along the flow’s path have been set to the *READY* state. When the first INT node receives a packet while being in the *READY* state, it emits an *INIT* signal which advances all INT nodes (on the path) to the *INSERT* state. Now the next packet of the flow encounters the first INT node in the *INSERT* state. As such, the INT node inserts its own telemetry value(s) into the packet. At the same time, the INT node transitions to the *INSERTED* state. This packet remains intact while traversing the remaining INT nodes, since they observe the

FIGURE 7. Resetting of INT node telemetry states, upon the completion of a monitoring round. A RESET signal is inserted by the last INT node into an ACK packet that resets all INT nodes to the READY state. This process triggers the advancement to a new round of monitoring.

encapsulated INT header and, thereby, refrain from inserting their own telemetry data (in order to avoid any inflation in the INT header size). This process is illustrated in Fig. 6 (upper packet).

The next packet initially reaches the first INT node (lower packet in Fig. 6). Since *node1* is in the *INSERTED* state, no telemetry action is applied to this packet (*i.e.*, it is merely forwarded to the next hop). Since the next INT node (*node2*) is in the *INSERT* state, it first checks whether an INT header has been appended in the packet, and, since this is not the case here, it encapsulates an INT header adding its own telemetry data. The packet will simply traverse the other INT nodes (*node3–node5*), as they will identify the INT header. Similar telemetry actions take place for the following packets, which will end up carrying the telemetry data of one of the following INT nodes. Then all INT nodes will be switched to the *INSERTED* state, which marks the completion of this monitoring round (an entire path trace will be conveyed to the telemetry server).

The transition to a new round of monitoring requires the resetting of all INT nodes along the path to the *READY* state. To this end, the last INT node on the path encodes a *RESET* signal into a TCP ACK packet, which flows in the reverse direction of the data traffic, *i.e.*, traversing all INT nodes in the reverse order as shown in Fig. 7 (we discuss later the case of path asymmetry and its potential implications). In essence, this process is repeated till the expiration of each flow, facilitating the graceful advancement to the next monitoring round, and eventually, the uninterrupted delivery of telemetry data.

VI. DISCUSSION

In this section, we discuss additional features of CLINT, as well as potential implications stemming from various conditions or incidents, such as path asymmetry or path updates during critical stages of CLINT (*e.g.*, *SETUP* phase).

A. MULTIPLE TELEMETRY VALUES

So far, we exemplified the operation of CLINT with the insertion of a single telemetry value per packet (*i.e.*, a single hop ID in the case of path tracing). This obviously ensures a minimal INT header size, but in certain cases, a network operator may permit a larger INT header that can accommodate either multiple hop IDs or a hop ID in conjunction with other telemetry data (*e.g.*, timestamps) that empower other means of monitoring.

The presence of a telemetry controller in our architecture greatly facilitates the specification of the INT header limit. This merely boils down to an incremental update in the interaction between the controller and the first INT node during the *SETUP* phase. More precisely, besides the allocation of telemetry space in the register array of the INT node, the controller can embed in the same message the INT metadata stack, in a similar way to P4-INT (albeit with confined INT metadata fields to maintain a compact INT header).

As such, CLINT can be configured to either convey more dense telemetry information for a certain type of telemetry application (*e.g.*, path tracing) or combine telemetry values for multiple applications. In our evaluation (Section VIII), we quantify the potential benefits stemming from multiple telemetry slots within the INT header (we particularly conduct tests with telemetry slots ranging from one to five).

Furthermore, a multi-slot INT header can be capitalized for more efficient header space utilization during the transmission of INT signals. For example, telemetry data can be encapsulated directly into the *INIT* signal (emitted by the first INT node on the path), obviating the need to wait for the following packet. In this case, the initial INT node will eventually advance two positions in the CLINT state-space (*i.e.*, it will transition from *READY* to *INSERTED*).

Multiple telemetry values can be also exploited as a remedy for the problem of monitoring very short flows. Considering an INT header with a single slot, a path trace of a flow with fewer packets than its path's hop-count will always be incomplete. However, an INT header that can accommodate multiple telemetry values could easily rectify this problem.

B. PATH ASYMMETRY

Recall that the *RESET* signal traverses the INT nodes in the reverse direction in order to reset them to the *READY* state. We hereby examine the potential implications in the case of path asymmetry, which would inhibit the *RESET* signal to traverse the INT nodes that have been previously utilized for the monitoring of a flow. In this case, there would be no implication as long as the *RESET* signal is able to reach the first INT node. That is, after resetting the first INT node (*i.e.*, to the *READY* state), an *INIT* signal will be immediately emitted which will flow in the forward direction, reverting all INT nodes into the *INSERT* state.

C. PATH UPDATES

We further discuss the impact of path updates during critical phases of CLINT. In particular, we focus on the *SETUP* phase, which initializes the telemetry states on all INT nodes on per-flow basis. Recall that each INT node sends a digest message to the controller, each time it observes a new flow. Path changes during the *SETUP* phase will not cause any implication, since the *FIN-SETUP* will follow the new path, augmenting the completion of the telemetry setup.

A potential implication, though, could occur at the event of a path update after the completion of the *SETUP* phase.

FIGURE 8. Compilation procedure and interface with the telemetry controller.

In this case, the INT nodes along the non-overlapping part of the two paths will not be set up telemetry-wise (*i.e.*, they will not be in the *SETUP* state). This problem can be detected, when an *INIT* signal is received by an INT node without any telemetry state installed for this flow. In this case, the specific INT nodes(s) will follow the standard telemetry setup process of CLINT, *i.e.*, they will send a digest message to controller. The latter can be programmed to mitigate this synchronization problem arising from the path update (*i.e.*, not all INT nodes along a path maintain up-to-date telemetry state for a given flow). More precisely, the controller could remove the telemetry state for the particular flow from all INT nodes, enforcing the telemetry setup from the beginning. Certainly, this remedy may cause an extra delay in the delivery of telemetry data; however, it will ensure that all telemetry information is accurate and consistent.

VII. IMPLEMENTATION DETAILS

In this section, we discuss some implementation details of our CLINT prototype, the challenges that we faced, as well as the solutions that we have eventually adopted. Although the development of the P4 ecosystem is still in progress, an experimental software P4 switch (BMv2) has been developed by a community led by the P4 Consortium [30].

Several technologies are utilized in the implementation of a network with P4 switches and the appropriate messaging with the controller. A P4 program goes through a compiler (p4c) and exports two files. The first (JSON) file describes the switch’s operation and is the equivalent to a binary for a hardware switch. The file is used as input to the BMv2 Simple Switch, which implements the switch’s logic. The second file (*p4info*) describes the specifics of the runtime communication between the controller and the switch. Tables, actions, parameters and everything that a controller can modify within a switch through the P4Runtime API is described here and is implemented over gRPC calls [31]. The API is conveniently defined in Protocol Buffers [32], which facilitates the transmission and rapid development of controller API procedures.

In our testing environment, multiple P4 switch instances are realized using the Mininet network emulator [33]. The

FIGURE 9. Sequence of switch IDs reaching the telemetry server using PINT, DLINT, and CLINT.

controller, which is implemented in Python, creates one thread for each switch that listens to its RPC port. When a switch receives a packet from an unknown flow, it sends a *digest* message with its 5-tuple to the controller. A *digest* message, defined in P4Runtime, is utilized to convey limited information to the controller without cloning the whole packet. Upon receiving the *digest*, the controller deciphers the parameters and adds them in a queue for processing. Subsequently, it responds with populating the INT table of the switch with the position of its register array, where this flow’s state should be stored. The following packets of the flow match the record in the *INT Match-Action* table and, as such, the telemetry process continues.

As TCP traffic flows in both directions, the path of each flow is traced separately per direction and as such, two different sets of telemetry states are required. Although the TCP traffic in the reverse direction may take a different path than the packets in the forward direction, we chose to proactively insert INT table entries in pairs of consequent positions in the register array for simplicity, as well as for the reduction of controller traffic.

VIII. EVALUATION

In this section, we perform a comparative evaluation of CLINT against two prominent lightweight INT methods, *i.e.*, PINT [11] and DLINT [12]. In particular, PINT represents a state-of-the-art probabilistic approach for INT transmission overhead reduction without any coordination among the INT nodes. Instead, DLINT relies on telemetry states to coordinate INT data encapsulation among a sequence of INT nodes. In contrast to CLINT, DLINT does not utilize any controller and relies solely on the data plane. Further information about the operation of PINT and DLINT can be found in Section III.

All the functionality of CLINT, PINT, and DLINT has been implemented on the BMv2 P4 software switch [34]. For our evaluations, we rely on Mininet [33], where we have emulated the BTN network topology, consisting of 27 nodes [35]. We particularly inject TCP traffic (using D-ITG [36]), consisting of 400 TCP flows spread over four intersecting paths. Flow size follows the Zipf distribution, which according to evidence (*e.g.*, [37]) characterizes the (flow size) distribution of Internet traffic. The duration of each experiment is 60 seconds. In addition, we rely on Python for the implementation of the telemetry controller for CLINT

and the overall instrumentation for the collection of our measurements.

A. PATH TRACE OBSERVATIONS

Before delving into the analysis of our experimental results, we take a first look at the efficiency of the three INT methods under comparison. In this respect, we illustrate path traces recorded by each one of the INT methods (Fig. 9). Each cell in the trace represents the content of the INT header, which may carry either a hop ID or a telemetry signal (there is also a third possibility, at which the header is vacant, as we see later on).

Recall that PINT inserts telemetry data with a predefined probability; as such, the INT header always carries telemetry value(s), since there is no need to emit any telemetry signal. Besides this observation, it is evident in Fig. 9 that telemetry values (*i.e.*, hop IDs in our example) are inserted randomly within the packets. An important implication here is that a given path trace can encompass duplicate hop IDs, as shown in Fig. 9. This stems from the reservoir sampling technique employed by PINT; this is utilized to ensure an equal probability of inserting telemetry metadata among all INT nodes along a path. As such, the number of packets required to convey a whole path to the telemetry server is likely to exceed the path hop-count (as shown in the path trace recorded by PINT in Fig. 9).

On the other hand, DLINT can deliver path traces with ordered sequences of switch IDs without any duplicates, as depicted in the first path trace captured by this INT mechanism (Fig. 9). Nevertheless, at the event of BF collisions, the recording of sequential monitoring data can be disrupted, as shown in DLINT's second path trace in Fig. 9. This eventually can lead to the encapsulation of duplicate INT values, wasting INT header space. Another (minor) implication of DLINT is the consumption of INT headers for the transmission of telemetry signals (*e.g.*, *INIT*).

CLINT exhibits a more deterministic behavior compared to PINT and DLINT. As shown in Fig. 9, CLINT delivers path traces, absent of duplicate telemetry values, consisting of ordered sequences of hop IDs. This is mainly attributed to the telemetry controller which is responsible for the setup of the telemetry operation, as exemplified in Section V-A. In essence, by utilizing a controller, CLINT avoids the intricacies of PINT and DLINT, stemming from its probabilistic nature and BF collisions, respectively. One shortcoming of CLINT, though, is that during the telemetry setup, there is no telemetry data encoded into the packets (see the beginning of the trace captured by CLINT in Fig. 9). Nevertheless, this implication could only have an impact on the monitoring of very short flows (where the number of recorded path traces will be very small, hence, any missing hop IDs would make a difference). Similar to DLINT, as CLINT relies on telemetry signals for INT node coordination, it occupies INT header space for their transmission.

FIGURE 10. Number of paths conveyed by CLINT, DLINT, and PINT, with a diverse range of telemetry slots (1–5).

B. MONITORING EFFICIENCY

We proceed with the assessment of monitoring efficiency using our evaluation environment. To this end, we initially measure the number of path traces conveyed to the telemetry server by each INT technique. This metric essentially captures the density and accuracy of telemetry data. Subsequently, we perform another set of tests to assess path update detection. More precisely, we trigger a path update in the middle of the experiment, and examine to what extent this path update has been detected by each INT method. In addition, we measure and report the path update detection responsiveness, *i.e.*, the time interval between the path update occurrence and its detection. Note that all tests are conducted with a diverse number of telemetry slots, ranging from 1 to 5, which essentially permit the encapsulation of multiple telemetry values (*e.g.*, hop IDs) within the INT header. This enables us to quantify any potential gains (both in terms of path tracing efficiency and path update detection) from the encapsulation of more dense telemetry information.

1) DENSITY AND ACCURACY OF TELEMETRY DATA

We initially examine the number of path traces conveyed by CLINT, DLINT, PINT. Since DLINT is susceptible to BF collisions, we conduct tests with diverse BF sizes and include the corresponding results in our plots.³ According to Fig. 10, CLINT delivers the larger number of paths in comparison to DLINT and PINT. This observation is prevalent for the whole range of telemetry slots (*i.e.*, 1–5). In principle, encoding more telemetry values per packet enhances monitoring efficiency. However, it can be observed that the number of path traces do not increase proportionally to the number of telemetry values. This stems from the fact that certain telemetry slots within the INT header may remain empty, since in most cases the path hop-count will not be an exact multiple of the number of telemetry slots per packet

³The number next to DLINT indicates the percentage of flows with respect to the number of BF entries (*i.e.*, DLINT-10 implies a large BF, DLINT-100 a medium-size BF, whereas DLINT-1000 a small BF).

FIGURE 11. Number of switch IDs conveyed by CLINT, DLINT, and PINT, with a diverse range of telemetry slots (1–5).

FIGURE 12. Percentage of duplicate switch IDs with a diverse range of telemetry slots (1–5).

(which comprises the primary condition for the full utilization of the INT header space in the presence of multiple telemetry slots).

The monitoring efficiency of DLINT is significantly affected by the BF size, as shown in Fig. 10. A large BF (DLINT-10) minimizes BF collisions and ensures an uninterrupted delivery of path tracing data. In this case, DLINT exhibits a nearly deterministic behavior and its path tracing efficiency is almost on par with CLINT (which slightly outperforms DLINT in this case). However, with a medium-sized (DLINT-100) and especially with a small BF (DLINT-1000), DLINT conveys a substantially lower number of path traces, suffering from BF collisions that disrupt the delivery of path tracing data.

PINT also falls short in terms of path trace delivery. According to Fig. 10, CLINT conveys at least twice as many path traces as PINT. In essence, PINT suffers from its own inherent probabilistic characteristics: the acquisition of an entire path trace by the telemetry server requires the delivery of more telemetry values compared to CLINT and DLINT, due to PINT’s telemetry data redundancy (see the path traces in Fig. 9).

We also conduct a more fine-grained examination of the telemetry data conveyed by each INT method. To this end, we measure the density of telemetry data, which, in case of path tracing, is quantified by the number of switch IDs delivered by CLINT, DLINT, and PINT (Fig. 11). With respect to DLINT, this density is dependant on the BF size, *i.e.*, BF collisions emerging from smaller BF sizes diminish the amount of telemetry data conveyed to the telemetry server. In this case, DLINT’s degradation (as BF size decreases) does not exhibit the steepness observed in Fig. 10. This stems from the fact that not all delivered switch IDs effectively contribute to the path trace composition (*e.g.*, DLINT may deliver duplicate switch IDs, due to BF collisions, which are utilized only in part).

On the contrary, CLINT being free of collision events (during state lookup) is able to match and, in certain occasions, even exceed DLINT (with a large BF) in terms of telemetry data density. Note that in the case of CLINT, not only the telemetry data conveyed is characterized by high density, but it is also fully utilized in the construction of each path trace at the telemetry server.

That said, PINT is the INT method that yields the higher telemetry data density by a notable margin, as illustrated in Fig. 11. This result may initially appear to be surprising, given the inferior performance of PINT based on Fig. 10. The discrepancy between PINT’s efficiency in terms of paths and switch ID is attributed to its telemetry data redundancy. Our corresponding results (Fig. 12) indicate that this redundancy of PINT is substantial (*i.e.*, nearly at a level of 40% over the total number of switch ID conveyed). As such, only a fraction of the telemetry data of PINT is utilized in the path trace composition. This observation is consistent with our logs, which indicate a significantly larger number of telemetry values per path trace, in comparison with CLINT and PINT.

2) PATH UPDATE DETECTION

We hereby assess the efficiency of CLINT, DLINT, and PINT in terms of path update detection. To this end, we initially measure among the number of flows that experienced a path update the percentage of flows at which this update has been detected by each one of the INT methods. According to Fig. 13, CLINT and PINT yield a very high path update detection accuracy, which is slightly enhanced in the presence of multiple telemetry slots. On the other hand, DLINT is on par with the other two INT methods only when it is equipped with a large BF (*i.e.*, DLINT-10). Instead, smaller BFs deteriorate significantly the detection accuracy of DLINT, as shown in Fig. 13.

Furthermore, we quantify the responsiveness of the INT methods from the perspective of path update detection. In this respect, Fig. 14 illustrates the time required for the detection of a path update (recall that this represents the interval between the instance that the update took place and the time of its detection). CLINT exhibits very high responsiveness (*i.e.*, the detection interval is less than 200 msec), outperforming PINT and DLINT with a medium-sized and large BF.

FIGURE 13. Percentage of flows for which the path update has been detected (with telemetry slots ranging from 1 to 5).

FIGURE 14. Time required for the detection of a path update (with telemetry slots ranging from 1 to 5).

It is worth noting that CLINT yields very a quick response even with a single telemetry slot, which is crucial when a very compact INT header is required or in cases that only one telemetry slot is available for path tracing (leaving the rest of INT header space for other types of telemetry metadata, such as timestamps).

C. HEADER SPACE UTILIZATION

Furthermore, we also perform a comparison between CLINT, DLINT, and PINT, in terms of INT header space utilization. More specifically, we measure the percentage of INT header space occupied by useful telemetry values (i.e., hop IDs), with telemetry slots ranging from one to five. Otherwise, a telemetry slot may accommodate a telemetry signal (e.g., INIT) or can be also empty (for different reasons that we explain later on). Both of these cases are considered as wasted space in the INT header.

Fig. 15 illustrates the INT header space utilization with the three INT methods. PINT exhibits a superiority in this respect, stemming from the absence of telemetry signals and the use of reservoir sampling, which ensures that all telemetry

FIGURE 15. INT header space utilization with a diverse range of telemetry slots (1-5).

slots will be filled with metadata by the time that each packet has reached the INT Sink. This observation holds for the entire range of telemetry slots for PINT.

CLINT and DLINT yield lower efficiency in terms of header space utilization, which decreases as telemetry slots increase. As hinted earlier, this is attributed to the following reasons: (i) both CLINT and DLINT use space from the INT header to carry various telemetry signals, (ii) CLINT and DLINT leave empty slots when the path hop-count is not an exact multiple of the number of telemetry slots, and (iii) CLINT starts encapsulating telemetry data after a short interval, required for the completion of telemetry setup, which involves the telemetry controller and all INT nodes. According to Fig. 15, the header space utilization of DLINT is slightly improved with a small BF (i.e., DLINT-1000). This mainly stems from DLINT’s BF collisions that tend to repeat parts of the path trace and, therefore, lead to better utilization.

However, this gain of PINT in terms of header space utilization is not translated to monitoring efficiency. As discussed earlier, the main reason behind this discrepancy is the high degree of telemetry data redundancy that PINT exhibits (see Fig. 12). A similar observation can be made for DLINT with a small BF, where BF collisions take a toll, disrupting the sequence of encapsulated switch IDs (leading to duplicate telemetry values, which is corroborated by Fig. 12).

D. CONTROL COMMUNICATION OVERHEAD

Finally, we provide a few measurements with respect to the control communication overhead, i.e., the volume of traffic exchanged between the telemetry controller and each INT node during the telemetry setup phase. More specifically, our measurements indicate that only 1.2 KB is exchanged per INT node and per flow. This encompasses the transmission of a digest message from an INT node to the controller, as well as the controller’s response that populates the telemetry state into the INT node’s registers. With such a minimal amount of traffic (per flow), any telemetry setup that involves multiple INT nodes or multiple flows (at the same time) raises no concern in terms of control communication overhead.

Additional control-plane traffic is exchanged between the controller and INT nodes for their binding and the termination of their connection. Again, our measurements reveal that this aspect of communication overhead is negligible. Overall, these measurements indicate that the intervention of the telemetry controller does not introduce any significant implications in terms of traffic generation in the network.

IX. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we discussed the design and implementation of a new lightweight INT technique, termed as CLINT. CLINT relies on the notion of per-flow aggregation in order to alleviate the substantial transmission overhead of P4-INT and other INT mechanisms that allow each packet to accumulate per-hop telemetry indicators across multiple INT nodes. In relation to other INT approaches that also harness per-flow aggregation (e.g., PINT, DLINT, PLINT [11], [12]), CLINT utilizes a centralized telemetry controller, which augments INT nodes with the coordination of telemetry actions on incoming packets. More specifically, the controller reserves telemetry state space at each INT node on per-flow basis, effectively bootstrapping the entire telemetry process. This is achieved through the combination of switch-controller interaction and INT node signalling. During the phase following telemetry setup (termed as *Monitoring* phase), the controller stays out of the loop leaving the task of telemetry action synchronization to the INT nodes, which observe and update the telemetry states for the repeated recording of telemetry indicators based on a pre-defined INT header budget (expressed in terms of telemetry slots).

Our experimental results corroborate the efficacy of this controller-assisted INT approach. More specifically, CLINT is benchmarked against representative lightweight INT techniques that either perform INT node telemetry-wise coordination through the data plane (i.e., DLINT) or resort to probabilistic techniques for the spreading of telemetry data among INT nodes, obviating the need for any coordination (i.e., PINT). CLINT yields high density in its delivered telemetry data and also achieves high utilization of its INT header space, on par with DLINT which is more comparable in this aspect (i.e., as both spare a small fraction of the INT header space for the transmission of telemetry signals). CLINT also exhibits very high responsiveness in the detection of network updates (we particularly measured the reaction to path updates), which is more remarkable with a single telemetry slot in the INT header. However, the aspect at which CLINT stands out is its ability to eliminate any redundancy among the encapsulated telemetry values. This means that any telemetry indicators conveyed to the telemetry server are all usable, effectively contributing to the construction of monitoring information (e.g., path traces). This strength empowers CLINT to convey more path traces than PINT, although the latter is able to deliver a larger number of telemetry values (e.g., switch IDs). Since the controller intervention in CLINT is restricted only in

the telemetry setup, the control communication overhead remains insignificant, as indicated by our measurements.

Overall, CLINT is able to capitalize the benefits of per-flow aggregation for lightweight INT, while avoiding the shortcomings of other INT approaches that hinder a deterministic INT behavior. Eventually, our approach challenges (to some extent) the status-quo in INT by demonstrating that a (centralized) telemetry controller can be an important asset of a lightweight INT platform.

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